
AN INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF CLIMATE CHANGE ON SELECTED CEREAL CROPS YIELD IN NIGERIA: A RICARDIAN ANALYSIS

Ajetomobi, J. O. and S. O. Binuomote

Department of Agricultural Economics, Ladoko Akintola University of Technology, P. M. B. 4000, Ogbomoso, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

In this research, we employed a statistical approach to examine the relationship between the yield of selected cereal crops and temperature (in centigrade) and precipitation (in millimeters) for the period 1995 – 2006 in Nigeria. The analyses focused on maize, rice, millet and guinea corn for all the states in Nigeria for the period of 1995 -2006. Data for annual yield of selected cereal crops for all the time period were collected from the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (N.B.S). Data on the two important climate variables required for crop growth - temperature and precipitation – used for the analysis were obtained from the Nigerian Metrological Agency. The response of cowpea yield to climate change varied from one geographical location to the other. The results indicated positive response of the yield of the cereal crops to increase in temperature which is possibly due to other factors that serve in cushioning the effect of the temperature such as irrigation; rainfall has positive relationship with the yield of the cereal crops except for millet; the positive coefficient of trend variable shows a positive relationship with the yield of selected cereal crops. The results of the elasticity of cereals yield to climate variables show that the yield of rice is inelastic to rainfall but negatively elastic to temperature. However, while maize, millet and guinea corn yield are not appreciably elastic to precipitation they were elastic to temperature changes. These results also reveal that with the passage of years and climate factors running contrary to agricultural productivities, cereal crops farmers in Nigeria were adopting new measures to cope with the negative effect of climate change. Climate adaptation measures include the use of drought or heat resistant varieties, early sowing, mixed cropping, tillage system alteration and the utilization of land that has been considered too marginal for agricultural cultivation reduces the negative effects of climate change on cereal crops yield and enhance the positive factors.

KEYWORDS: Climate change, Cereal crops, Ricardian, Nigeria

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Corresponding Author: sobinuomote@lautech.edu.ng

INTRODUCTION

Climate change impact studies have shown that the productivity of agricultural activities is highly sensitive to climate change. The effect of changes in climate on agricultural activities both physical and economic has been shown to be significant for low input farming systems, such as subsistence farming in developing countries in sub-Saharan Africa that are located in marginal areas and have the least capacity to adapt to changing climatic conditions (Rosenzweig and Parry 1994; Reilly and Schimmelpfennig 1999; Kates 2000; McGuigan *et al* (2002).

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Because most developing countries are heavily dependent on agriculture, the effect of climate change on their productive croplands is likely to threaten economic development and the welfare of the population. In addition, developing countries in tropical regions usually have large areas of poor marginal soils that are unusable for agriculture, which makes them particularly vulnerable to potential damage from environmental changes (Mendelsohn and Dinar 1999). The importance of agriculture for the economies of most African countries and the farming sector's reliance on the quality of rains during the rainy season make Zimbabwe and other countries in the region particularly sensitive to climate change and food insecure (Mendelsohn *et al.* 2000).

The effect of climate change on agricultural systems can be seen in the interaction between changes in climate variables and the stresses that result from actions taken to increase agricultural production. Impacts on crop yields, agricultural productivity and food security vary depending on the types of agricultural practices and systems (Watson *et al.* 1997). There is growing evidence that further increases in global warming leading to changes in main climate variables – temperature, precipitation, sea level rise, atmospheric carbon dioxide content and incidence of extreme events – may significantly affect African agricultural production (Watson *et al.* 1997), with the result that the livelihoods of subsistence farmers and pastoral peoples, who make up a large portion of rural populations in sub-Saharan Africa, could be negatively affected.

Climate change is a threat to agricultural and socioeconomic development; agricultural production activities are generally more vulnerable to climate change than other sectors (IPCC 1990, Derresa *et al.*, 2005). Similarly, the effect of climate change on vegetation can be dramatic, due to variations in the amount of CO₂ available for photosynthesis. In addition, climatic factors such as temperature, precipitation, moisture and pressure affect the development of plants, either alone or by interacting with other factors (Cutforth, 2007).

In Nigeria, agriculture is the main source of food and employer of labour, employing about 60-70 per cent of the population. It is a significant sector of the economy and the source of raw materials used in the processing industries as well as a source of foreign exchange earnings for the country (Mohammed-Lawal and Atte, 2006). Since agriculture in Nigeria is mostly rain-fed, it follows therefore that any change in climate is bound to impact its productivity in particular and other socio-economic activities generally, in the country. The issue of climate change has become more threatening not only to the sustainable development of socio-economic and agricultural activities of any nation but also to the totality of human existence (Adejuwon, 2004). As further explained by Adejuwon(2004), the effect of climate change implies that the local climate variability which people have previously experienced and adapted to is changing and this change is observed in a relatively great speed.

Evidence has shown that climate change has already affecting crop yields in many countries (IPCC, 2007; Deressa *et al.*, 2008; BNRCC, 2008). This is particularly true in low-income countries, where climate is the primary determinant of agricultural productivity and adaptive capacities are low (SPORE, 2008; Apatae *et al.*, (2009). Many African countries, which have their economies largely based on weather-sensitive agricultural productions systems like Nigeria, are particularly vulnerable to climate change (Dinar *et al.*, 2006). Climate change may also change the types, frequencies, and intensities of various crop and livestock pests; the availability and timing of irrigation water supplies; and the severity of soil erosion (Silayo *et al.*, 2008).

Subsistence or cereal crops like maize and rice, which provide a third of the national daily calorific intake and are grown by half of the farmers, could be particularly affected by climate change National Adaptation Programme of Action (NAPA) (URT, 2007) indicated that with an increase in temperature and reduced rainfall, as well as change in rainfall patterns, the average yield would decrease by 33% countrywide. Ajetomobi *et al.*, (2010) found that increase in temperature due to extreme climatic events may undermine any positive effects by reducing the net revenue for dry land rice farms, whereas increase revenue for the irrigated rice farms due to the fact that, irrigation

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buffers the crop from rainfall shortages. Precipitation had similar effects on rice net revenue in dry land and irrigated production systems or hilly regions in semi-arid regions (Ajetomobi *et al*, 2010).

Nigerian's economy is dependent on the climate, because a large proportion of GDP is associated with climate sensitive activities, particularly agriculture. As a result, current climate variability such as droughts and floods, has led to major economic losses in Nigeria. Furthermore, the occurrence of dry-spell any time during the growing season as impact of climatic changes often exposes crops to moisture stress, hence farmers usually face problems of both too much and little moisture (Watkiss, 2011). These effects have necessitated changes in the way smallholder rice farmers make decision to adapt to their environment (Ajetomobi *et al*, 2010). Therefore, farmers apply different strategies to adapt and cope with the challenges of climate change and the strategies opted are for example; combining less productive drought-resistant cultivars with high yield but water-sensitive crops (Kuponiyi *et al.*, 2010; Mbilinyi *et al.*, 2010). In the light of this, this study will shed more light on the effect of climate change on cereal production in Nigeria

METHODOLOGY

The Research Area and its Climatic Structure

Nigeria is located on the southern coast of West Africa between 2° and 15°E longitude and 5° and 15°N latitude. Benin borders to the west, Niger to the North and Chad and Cameroon to the area of over 923,773 square kilometers extensively within the tropical zone. It extends north wards from the coastline for over 140km. Nigeria's area of land is about 98 million hectares, with about 75 percent suitable for cultivation of almost all typical crops, out of which only 14 percent is under cultivation in any form, 1.4 million hectares is estimated to be irrigable; only 0.05% of the cultivated hectares are presently under irrigation, most of the irrigable and irrigated land are the Northern states of the country (Fabiya *et al*, 2011).

Surface water resources total about 193 billion cubic meters based on annual flow of the country's rivers and streams. The figure (193 billion m³) excludes soil moisture and ground water. It is estimated that about 95% of surface water in the Northern states can be controlled.

The climate of the country studies from a fairly wet coastal area with annual rainfall greater than 3500mm to the Sahel region in the north western and northeastern parts with annual rainfall of less than 600mm. (Ajetomobi 2010).

By virtue of Nigeria's location primarily within the lowland humid tropics, the country is generally characterized by a high temperature regime almost through the year. In the far south, mean maximum temperature is between 30°C and 32°C while in the north it is between 36°C and 38°C. However, the mean minimum temperature is between 20°C and 22°C in the south and under 13°C in the north which has a much higher annual range. The mean temperature for the country is between 27°C and 29°C.

In the absence of altitudinal modifications, the diverse nature of the country's climate consequently give rise to a high degree of biological diversity mainly in six vegetation zones; the mangrove swamps, Sudan savanna, the salt water and fresh water swamps, tropical lowland rainforests, guinea savanna and Sahel savanna. Salt and fresh water swamps are along the coast of Nigeria. The salt-water swamps stretch inland for 1-2 km in the Lagos area to over 30km in the Sapele area. Further inland beyond the reach of tidal waters, mangroves give way to fresh water plants, the most important of which is the raffia palm. From a water balance perspective, the country experiences large spatial and temporal variations in rainfall, and less variation in evaporation and evapo-transpiration. Consequently, rainfall is by far the most important element of climate in Nigeria and thereby becomes a critical index for assessing agricultural and water resources potential in the country.

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Nigerian cereal cropping dominates crop production in the northern part of the country; while the dominant crops in the south are cassava, yam, palm produce, rubber and cocoa. Agriculture in Nigerian economy has the same general characteristic as the country's economy those of a giant with feet of clay. While production has leap considerably over the past twenty-five years, demand has also risen, accentuating the federation's dependency on foreign cereal products and making it vulnerable to internal and external shocks. The significance of this sector in the economy follows, therefore, that any change in climate is bound to impact on the agricultural sector in particular and the socio-economic activities in general.

Description of Model for Climatic Factors Fluctuations

This study employed statistical model that relates yield per hectare to meteorological data (Torvanger *et al*, 2004) . The study assumed a quadratic relationship between yield per hectare, Y and temperature, T, precipitation, P, and a time trend, T. Annual mean temperature was measured in degree centigrade while precipitation was measured in millimeters.

The equation is

$$Y_{it} = a + b_j T_{ij} + c_j P_{ij} + d_j T_{jt}^2 + e_j P_{jt}^2 + \theta \tau + \omega_{jt}$$

Where j is the state index, t is the time index, denoting annual observations from 1995 to 2006. ω_{jt} is the error term.

The estimated parameters are a,b,c,d,e and θ . A time trend has been included in the model. This served as a proxy, for the non inclusion of some non climate variables which are important in agricultural productivity. Such factors include technological change and innovations (improvement in agricultural inputs/and or practices and/or changes in production patterns), increased productivity due to other climate variables and a fertilizer effect from increased CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere. Although sunlight is another important weather variable necessary for crop growth it was not possible to include it in the analysis because the meteorological stations did not have the data or its proxy for the period of the study.

Data Description and Sources

The dependent variable is yield per hectare of selected cereal crop while the explanatory variables are weather data, namely, annual mean temperature, measured in centigrade, the annual precipitation measured in millimeters and a time trend. All variables used in the regression model were time series covering the time period of 1995-2006. The analyses were based on all the state producing maize, rice, millet and guinea corn in Nigeria for the main period 1995-2006. Data for the total production of each crop per state and the total agricultural area per state for each crop were collected from the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics (N.B.S). The annual yield for each crop was estimated by dividing the total production of each crop per state by the total agricultural area employed in the cultivation of each crop in that state and was measured in kilogram per hectare.

Two important climate variables required for crop growth had been employed in this study. These are temperature and precipitation at state or regional level in Nigeria. The data were obtained from the Nigerian Metrological Agency as reported in the annual abstract of the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, covering the study period. Annual precipitation is measured in millimeters.

The second weather variable is temperature measured in centigrade. The precipitation used in the analysis is the annual precipitation rather than monthly precipitation for only the cropping months. This is because a significant part of the precipitation falling outside the cropping months will be retained inside the soil as moisture content and hence contributing to crop growth at the onset of the cropping seasons.

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Meteorological data used in the analysis were arranged according to phenological periods of the cereal investigated according to the examined period. All the data used in the study was related to the period 1995-2006.

Cereal yield was regressed on the climatic variables. The yield was the dependent variables of the regression model. Totally 4 different independent variables were used in the model. These independent variables were temperature (°C), rainfall (mm), square of temperature (°C), square of rainfall (mm) and time trend for land area, production and yield separately.

The a-priori expectation of the regression model is as follows:

Ri, rainfall is theorized to affect crop production positively. The basis for this theoretical expectation is justified with the fact that rainfall increase affects crop yield positively (IPCC, 2001a; IPCC, 2001b; Rosenzweig and Hillel, 1995) by readily dissolving the nutrients for easy soil absorption by plants.

Ti, Temperature is hypothesized to be positively related to crop production; the basis for this is that temperature benefits crop production by enhancing photosynthesis thereby increasing crop yield as it increases (Sombroek and Gommès, 1996; Rosenzweig and Hillel, 1995).

The linear term introduced into the model is expected to indicate the unidirectional impact of the independent variables on the dependent variable while the quadratic term is expected to reflect the impact of increase in the independent variables on the dependent variable as well as the non-linear shape of the yield as they respond to climate function. When the quadratic term is positive, the yield function is U shaped and when the quadratic term is negative, the function is hill-shaped. Agronomic studies have revealed that crops consistently exhibit a hill-shaped relationship with annual temperature, although the maximum of that hill varies with the crop.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The regression analysis that was employed to estimate the impact of climate change on cereal crop yield for this study was a linear (quadratic) model for ease of interpretation. The explanatory variables of climate include both the linear and quadratic temperature and rainfall term.

The model is specify as follows

$$Y_{ij} = a + b_j T_{ij} + c_j P_{ij} + d_j T_{jt}^2 + e_j P_{jt}^2 + \theta \tau + \omega_{jt}$$

Where: Y = yield per hectare

T = Temperature

P = Precipitation

τ = Trend

ω_{jt} - Random error

The model relate yield per hectare to meteorological data. Annual mean temperature was measured in degree centigrade while precipitation was measured in millimeters. 1 and 2 are the state index

Estimate of the Parameters and Discussion of findings

Table 1 shows that the result of the Ricardian analysis which shows the relationship between yield of selected crops and the different climatic variables as shown in the model specification. While the relationship with rainfall is positive and significant at 10% which is also in line with theoretical expectation, the relationship between yield of rice and square of temperature is negative. The result suggests that excessive temperature will have negative effect on rice yield.

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The negative relationship between the yield of the cereal crops and temperature is expected given the extremely high temperature as a result of intense sunshine and desertification in most region of the country producing cereal in large quantities. Higher temperature can also cause earlier flowering and flower abscission, higher rate of evapotranspiration resulting in poor grain. High night temperature can cause flower abscission in some cultivars during flowering. The positive response of the yield of the cereal crops to increase in temperature can be probably attributed to other factors that serve in cushioning the effect of the temperature; for instance, irrigation system. The use of irrigation water helps the crop to cope with heat stress that comes due to a temporary drought that exists in some of the state such as August breaks and or intense sunshine.

Rainfall has positive relationship with the yield of the cereal crops except for millet. However, at increased rainfall, the yields of the selected cereal crops are seen to be fallen as shown in the table 1 above. The result suggests that while the other crops might do well at relatively and moderate levels of rainfall, millet requires more water supplies. However, since millet is mostly cultivated in northern Nigeria, irrigation might be making up for the increased water need of millet ahead of others. The negative coefficient of rainfall may also not be surprising because the growing season of cereal crops sometimes coincide with the period of heavy rain usually accompanied by heavy water logs and leaching which is not a conducive environment for cereal crop production.

Also, the positive coefficient of trend variable shows that as years went by and climatic factors ran contrary to agricultural productivities, cereal crops farmers were also adopting new measures to cope with the negative effect of climatic change. For instance, the use of fertilizer, and adoption of improved farming practices- early maturing cultivars, mulching, irrigation practices relate the positive correlation of the time trend with the yield of the cereal crop.

Rice crop can be grown successfully where average air temperature is 21°C for 5-6 months. The critical mean temperature for flowering and fertilization ranges from 16-20°C. For its vegetative growth, a temperature range of 25-30°C is suitable and as well for grains filling and ripening. The best temperature for higher yield is a day temperature of 25-32°C and night temperature of 15-20°C. At temperature less than 15°C will slow down flowering. Rice can stand water logged conditions; at least 200mm of monthly rainfall is suitable for lowland rice while 100mm is good for upland rice. It requires a rainfall of 25cm during vegetative stage. It is best suited for the region having high humidity and prolonged sunshine. Mean temperature around 22°C is suitable throughout the growing period but can tolerate day temperature of up to 40°C.

Maize thrives well in areas where mean daily temperature is less than 19°C; germination is faster were soil temperature is about 16-18°C. The critical temperature detrimentally affecting yield is approximately 30°C. Approximately 10-16 kg of grains are produced for every millimeter of water used. For a yield of 3,152 kg/ha requires between 350-450 mm of rain per annum. At maturity, each plant will have used 250/ of water in the absence of moisture stress. The suitable soil for maize is one with a good effective depth, favorable morphological properties, good internal drainage, an optimal moisture regime, sufficient and balanced quantities of plant nutrient and chemical properties that are favorable specifically for maize production.

Soil with clay content of less than 10% (sandy soils) or in excess of 30% (clay and clay-loam soils) is good for large scale production. Optimum P¹¹ is from 6.0-7.0, when the P^H is less than 5.5, many nutritional and growth problems begins to develop. Higher temperature can cause abnormalities like appearance of ear in tassel; the soil moisture must be continuous through out the growth period and is especially critical from silking through kernel growth. Water stress at silking can lead to poor pollination, which shows up later as missing kernels. At higher temperature above 35°C makes tip fill poor; water logged can lead to poor seed set whereas, noon temperature above 35°C for several days will destroy pollen and yield are drastically reduced.

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In the cases of millet and guinea corn production, they grow well on well-drained loamy soil and will not tolerate water-logged or extreme drought, coarse and sandy soil. It grows best at temperature which ranges from 20-28°C. Millet is more tolerant to higher temperature than any other cereal. They become dormant during moisture stress but revert to normalcy subsequently; the stage of germination, lowering and grain filling are critical periods for moisture stress. Temperature at 23°C is best for germination of millet seed. It requires optimum rainfall which ranges between 35-50 cm of annual rainfall and responds to good moisture supplies during growth. The ability of millet to grow in drier environment is due to a number of Biological and morphological characteristics, for instance; rapid and deep root penetration, root system with well developed and specialized cell wall that prevents desiccation.

The best yield can be achieved when the mean temperature is around 26-29°C during the growing period. It tolerate day temperature of up to 40°C while minimum of 8-10°C is good for germination.

Elasticities of Selected Cereal Crops to Climate Change

Elasticity gives the degree of percentage change in the dependent variable as a result of one percentage change in the independents variable. It is the degree of responsiveness of the cereals as a result of a percentage change in the climatic variables.

Table 2 shows that the yield of rice is inelastic to rainfall but negatively elastic to temperature. This means that a unit changes in the amount of rainfall result in a certain percentage change in quantity of rice yield. Elasticity of rainfall is in the same direction as rainfall change. However, one percent decrease in the degree of temperature produces a corresponding 6.55 percent increase in the level of rice yield.

Table 2 also shows that maize, millet and guinea corn yield are inelastic to precipitation but elastic to temperature changes. The result show that while a percentage change in the precipitation could not bring about a corresponding percentage change in the yields of maize, millet and guinea corn, one percent decrease in the amount of temperature will increase maize yield by 5.50 percent, millet yield by 2.90 percent and guinea corn yield by 6.83 percent respectively.

Table 1: Report of Crop Yield to Climate Change

Crop	Constant	Rainfall	Temperature	Square of Rainfall	Square of temperature	Trend	R ²
Rice	7.40 (1.91)	0.01* (3.09)	-0.33 (-1.51)	0.007* (-3.98)	0.004 (1.36)	0.00 (0.30)	0.06
Maize	6.72 (1.80)	0.01* (2.58)	-0.27 (-1.27)	0.005* (-2.41)	0.016 (0.95)	0.01 (1.04)	0.08
Millet	3.60 (1.09)	-0.014 (-0.40)	-0.10 (-0.55)	-6.85 (0.26)	0.00 (0.42)	0.02** (1.64)	0.02
Guinea Corn	6.43 (1.14)	0.002 (0.37)	-0.26 (-0.82)	-2.19 (-0.05)	0.00 (0.68)	0.01 (0.63)	0.02

Source: Data Analysis, 2014

*Indicates significance at 10%; **Indicates significance at 10%;

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Table 2: Elasticities of Yield to climate change

Yield Elasticity	Value
Rice – rainfall	0.60
Rice – temperature	-6.55
Maize – rainfall	0.50
Maize – temperature	-5.50
Millet – rainfall	-0.13
Millet – temperature	-2.90
Guinea corn – rainfall	0.20
Guinea corn – temperature	-6.83

Source: Data Analysis 2014

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The study carried out an econometric analysis of climate change impact on yields of selected cereal crops in Nigeria. The result of the study revealed that cereal response to climate change varies from one geographical region to the other and from crop to crop. The regression result indicated that the climate variables have significant impacts on the cereal yield and that yield is likely to respond to climate change in Nigeria. The result also showed that as the years went by and in the face of negative changes in climate factors relative to agricultural production, cereals farmers were adopting new measures to cope, adapting with the negative effect of climate change and mitigating the same. This is revealed in the positive effect of non - climate variables which are important in agricultural productivity captured by time trend in our model. Such factors include technological change and innovations (improvement in agricultural inputs/and or practices and/or changes in production patterns), increased productivity due to other climate variables and a fertilizer effect from increased CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere.

The study therefore suggests that the use of irrigation will be effective adaptation measures to reduce the harmful effect of climate change on cereal agriculture. Modern irrigation system can be used to offset excessive temperature where and when necessary. The Nigerian government should make effort to put the Nigerian river basins into effective usage.

The most important prerequisite for good crop production is the availability of good quality seed of high yielding varieties, adapted to the growing area; it is thus, recommended that choosing suitable cereal crop varieties and early maturing seed should be obtained from a reliable source because the quality of seeds alone is known to account for increase in productivity of at least 10-15 per cent. Good seed is the most important input in crop production since its potential, determined by genetic makeup, set upper limit of the yield attainable under the most conducive conditions. Government must therefore make good seed available to farmers at subsidized rate through national seed service.

Crop rotation practices should be sought among cereal farmers as an important tool of integrated management of cereal production; the rotation management will maintain soil condition, minimize risk of nitrite leaching and reduce pest development in order to optimize crop health. The use of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) System should also be encouraged.

Fertilization should be well balanced in order to provide the appropriate allowance of nutrients, also, chopping and incorporation of crop residue (mulching) as well as organic manure or compost will help improve soil fertility by increasing organic matter content, improve nutrient, water retention, reduced erosion and fluctuation in climatic conditions.

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Training and services by extension agent and field demonstration should be encouraged as this will significantly boost their farmers yield and income after all; The option establishment of plant clinics with competent pathologist, entomologist and soil scientist to give technical assistance to the farmers in terms of diagnosis, control, correct use of pesticides and the use of disease free planting materials should also be exploited

Above all, agro-metrological stations should be made available at district, local and regional level to help farmers in weather forecasting through crop performance in terms of (planting dates, yield, densities of sowing, location and acreages of planting), estimating probabilities of occurrence of potential hazards (frost, fire, hail, severe rainfall). This will help agriculture to make the most complete and rational use of climatic and weather data; to operate economically, produce high and consistent yields and to maximize their productivity. Through these adaptive measures discussed above, the negative effect of climate change on cereal agriculture could be reduced and the positive influences enhanced. And finally, wider research and deeper analyses regarding to climate change on agriculture should be encouraged.

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